

ISic3090

I.Sicily inscription 3090

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific (?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Cephaloedium

Place of origin (modern)

Cefalù

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Cefalù, Duomo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331406

1. [— — — — — — — — —]

2. καὶ οἱ ἄλλοι π [ολῖται(?)]

3. γραμματε [ὺς]

4. Γόργος Ζωΐ[λου].

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284916

EDCS 64900518

PHI 331406

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 36.0846

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1982. II materiale antico reimpiegato e rilavorato in età normanna - Iscrizioni greche. *Mostra di documenti e testimonianze figurative della Basilica Ruggeriana di Cefalù. Catalogo della mostra Cefalù, luglio - settembre 1982*. Palermo. pp. 63-64. At 64 ph

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3090. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388105>